

THE METHODOLOGY FOR USING RELIABLE AND INFORMATIVE TESTS IN THE SELECTION OF FOOTBALL FOR SPORTS

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Abstract: this article offers and recommendations on the selection and orientation of children in the sport of football.

Keywords: football, saralash, selection, orientation, prediction, management, racomylation

МЕТОДИКА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ НАДЕЖНЫХ И ИНФОРМАТИВНЫХ ТЕСТОВ ПРИ ВЫБОРЕ ФУТБОЛА ДЛЯ ЗАНЯТИЙ СПОРТОМ

Аннотация: в данной статье предложены и рекомендации по отбору и ориентации детей в спорте футбол.

Ключевые слова: футбол, саралаш, отбор, ориентация, прогнозирование, управление, ракомилирование.

The process of qualifying talented young people in the world, directing them to sports, is becoming one of the priority areas today. Leading scientists and specialists in the field of sports emphasize the need to train talented young players, taking into account the peculiarities of their physical development, physical fitness and effectiveness of their ability to move. The based methods of qualifying Sports-qualified children for sports schools, predicting their future achievements as well as their prospects in sports, are becoming an integral part of the multi-year training system. The system of rational selection and orientation to sports, the search for abilities and talent by nature are becoming one of the main indicators of the football of developed countries.

Many measures are being implemented in our republic aimed at attracting the growing young generation to sports in recent years and sorting out talented athletes from among young people. Special attention is paid to the issues of effective and transparent four-stage selection (selection) of talented athletes from among young people in places: development and implementation of the organization-District (City)-territory-Republic system "and" identification of talented athletes and creation of reserves for youth national teams". The lack of comprehensive, scientific and methodological work on the selection of talented children for football, in addition to the fact that in the process of sorting children for football, physical development, assessment of physical fitness indicators, a reanalysis of continuous monitoring indicators on these indicators are demanding the identification and implementation of reliable, informative tests that determine football-specific abilities. It also remains a requirement of the period to determine to what extent the indicators of their gradual physical development and physical fitness are as the main tool at the stage of sorting out the individual capabilities of young talented players, to carry out research work based on scientific and practical experience on the main stages of organizing an effective qualifying system.

The purpose of the study is to develop practical recommendations to improve the efficiency of qualifying 6-7-year-old players through the use of reliable and informative tests.

"The content and organization of the qualification of young players for sports" covers the problems of qualifying young players, general qualifying rounds, organizational and methodological aspects of qualifying for football, problems of preliminary selection and selection.

Based on an analysis of domestic and foreign literature, it was found that many professionals focus on identifying and looking for new forms and ways to control the physical development and physical fitness of children when sorting them into football. The organization and conduct of pedagogical control in the selection of children for football should be aimed at determining the abilities of children in the selection process, as well as achieving a high level of physical and special training. The main task is to determine to what extent the indicators of general and special training of young players are suitable. In this case, children should be engaged in football, the informativeness and reliability of the selected set of tests for sorting them should be tested. The level of physical fitness of children and adolescents is determined through control tests and pedagogical observations of testing their basic physical qualities. To determine the potential of children and adolescents with a high degree of probability, it is advisable to determine not only the level of their initial training, but also the pace of their growth. The ability to determine the ability to solve the tasks of movement, demonstrate the creativity of movement and control it should be revealed. In most cases, one-time control tests provide information about promising opportunities to stay ready to perform the presented set of tests. And the potential outcome of an athlete will depend more on the rate of growth of these qualities in the process of special training than the initial level of development of physical qualities.

According to most experts, sorting is a set of organizational and methodological measures of a complex nature, which includes pedagogical, sociological, psychological and medico - biological research methods, on the basis of which the predisposition and abilities of children to specialize in a particular sport are determined. At the same time, qualifying is a vital part of the training and training process, helping to achieve the main task of sports training-high sports results.

The analysis and study of scientific and methodological literature shows that a system of child qualifying tests was not created to deal with football, and the existing ones did not undergo a special examination for compliance with the requirements of the standardization criteria. For this reason, a clear system of sorting children to engage in football has not been created. Based on the above information, the study of this problem is considered relevant.

To date, the game of football has become even faster, which is manifested in the fact that in the first place there is a surge of play, athletes quickly make an effective decision, read the opponent's movement, struggle to choose the right place for the ball or from each part of the field. The active resistance of opponents, the high-speed implementation of each movement on the field, the correct choice of the place on the field (position), the large neuromuscular exhaustion caused by the complexity of technical and tactical actions when fighting for the ball further complicate the effectiveness of competition activities. The increase in the effectiveness of sports and gaming activities of players depends on the degree of development of several preparatory indicators. In football, a decent qualification at the initial preparatory stage is extremely important, because of the unreliability of the means and criteria used for zero qualifying, this should not lead to a stagnation in the growth of sportsmanship.

Table 1. Assessment of reaction time and time of selective reaction in technical actions performed on the legs in accordance with the situation in order to determine the physical qualities of talented players 6- years old criteria theoretical model

Special adjectives	Special features, manifestation of abilities	Criteria, tests, methodologies
	Increase movement speed and reactivity	Walking up 20 m.ga run

Agility, agility, durability		30 from high start m.ga run
	Increase movement agility and reactivity	3x10 m.ga mokisimon run
	Increase movement endurance	6-minute run through the stadium
Fast-power	Fighting and striking for the ball in the air	High jump from where you stand
		Jump long from where you stand
	Fighting for the ball in a short time on the move	Lifting the torso while lying on your back
	Introducing the ball into the game and passing it to the partner (fielder, goalkeeper	Hanging on the turnstile in bent hands
Shooting forward the filling Ball (1 kg) behind the head in both hands		
Reaction time of the legs	To'pni qabul qilish	Ball control in the air(playing ball
	Qisqa vaqt ichida to'pni darvozga tepish va sherigiga uzatish	Kicking the ball far on the right and left foot
	To'pni his etish, texnik harakatlarda qisqa vaqt ichida to'pni boshqarish	With three touches to the ball 30 m distance carry

At the time of qualifying for sports, the abilities of athletes will not be expressed equally brightly. This is primarily due to the fact that their mode of action, the pace of maturation, social and other factors differ from each other. The principle of a comprehensive approach to solving the issue of qualifying for sports allows not only to obtain a wide range of information, but also to compare indicators that relate to different areas of life activity in terms of the possibility of the formation of special abilities. All the qualities and properties of a person are in a complex relationship with each other and the effectiveness of gaming activities. They also undergo changes in the process of sports training. The laws of relationships and variability direct the correct and timely assessment of abilities in sorting.

In the development of sports qualification technology, its understanding as methods for assessing the capabilities of those engaged in the effective use of tools and methods for determining the prospects of athletes in order to effectively solve the tasks of sports training in stages and the final tasks of initial training of young players was the starting point.

Exercises and tests for complex control of functional and physical capabilities were developed and their reliability characteristics were considered. On the tests, which are recognized as reliable and informative, the effectiveness of the growth of physical development, physical fitness, technical actions, coordination indicators of young players has been comprehensively monitored.

Children's abilities during sorting will not be equally brightly expressed either. This is due to the fact that in the first goal, their mode of action, Growth Rates, social and other factors differ from each other.

Conclusion scientific and methodological literature and analysis of the practical experience of leading coaches showed that the need to develop a scientifically based methodology for sorting physical development, physical training and motor skills into sports training when sorting talented young players who are able to better adapt to the specific loads inherent in this sport and effectively realize their capabilities during the game became clear. Using exercises aimed at reducing the time of selective reaction to technical actions in accordance with the situation when training elements performed with the ball during pedagogical observation to increase the efficiency of qualifying young players, it is necessary to increase the speed-strength capabilities of players on the basis of a special physical quality development model, which was found to help not only increase the speed.

According to the structure of the technology for qualifying young players for sports at the initial preparatory stage, the technology for qualifying talented and promising young players is recommended to organize on the basis of four main components, namely: 1) goal, 2) diagnostics, 3) Assessment and prediction, 4) recommendations for decision-making. The level of mastery of technical movement skills, which allows 7-8-year-old players in the starting training group to perform rhythmic movements based on speed switching and dribbling, was determined using the practice of “bowling with the foot”, as well as a clear shot at the goal, kicking the ball into circles and squares arranged in different order, controlling the ball in when qualifying young players for the sport, it is necessary to have sufficient information about its order and sequence.

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